

MODERN TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ENERGY INDUSTRY IN THE WORLD

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Abstract: the article covers the need and importance of the transition to a green economy, the structure of the green economy and its important peculiarities, its importance in the development of countries, ensuring the stability of economic growth. The production of renewable energy sources has touched on the issues of reducing carbon emissions, ensuring energy efficiency.

Keywords: green economy, carbon monoxide, energy conservation, energy density, environmental change, climate change, green finance.

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In world practice, special importance is attached to the study of sustainable development of territories, their economic and environmental systems in their effective harmony. In particular, the development of countries directly depends on the stability of the regions, and the positive aspects of this issue include the rational and effective use of resources based on the expansion of the innovative economy. In particular, the correct Organization of production activities in the economy, ensuring the duration and growth of the industry depends on the availability of resources. This is due to the effective implementation of management decisions aimed at ensuring the harmony of economic and environmental systems in ensuring the stability of the regions.

Production of renewable energy sources reducing carbon emissions SO₂, increasing green-tech greenhouses, water recycling and delivery based on green technologies, "green" vehicles, car electrification, "green" households, production of clean environmental products in cities, production of environmentally friendly, organic food in agriculture are important today.

The formation of a "green" economy and the transition to its sustainable development are priorities both at the global level and for Uzbekistan. The concept of sustainable development is an important resource for the future of mankind, which is embodied in the decisions and documents of the UN. The economic and environmental basis of sustainable development is the formation and development of this "green" economy. To overcome current unstable trends, in 2015, specific UN

criteria for the development of 17 "green" economies for the period up to 2030 were identified.

The decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 2, 2022, PQ-436 "on measures to improve the efficiency of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a green economy by 2030" established the goals of transition to the green economy of Uzbekistan. According to this decision 2022 – Implementation of the tasks set out in the new Uzbekistan development strategy for 2026, increasing the efficiency of measures implemented to ensure green and inclusive economic growth within the framework of the transition strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a green economy, the use of renewable energy and further expansion of resource savings in all sectors of the economy, the program "transition to a green economy and Also, the goal was to reduce greenhouse gases by 35% compared to the level of previous years, increase the production capacity of renewable energy sources to 15 gvt, significantly increase the efficiency of water use in all sectors of the economy. Until 2030, the Republic of Uzbekistan set indicators for the transition to a "green" economy and ensuring "green" growth by 2030 to reduce the volume of energy per unit of GDP by 30% (compared to 2021), electricity consumption in the industry, reducing its share in total consumption by 20%, expanding the share of renewable energy in the total volume of electricity production by 30.5% (including hydropower).

The article focuses on the issues of the need for a green economy, its peculiarities, the transition to a "green" economy in industrial sectors, the maintenance of energy savings. As part of the research in this direction, the results of a number of previously carried out scientific research were studied.

Including M.A. In his research, Gureva cited a number of problems in the development of a "green" economy, citing as their solutions the introduction of fines for negatively affecting the environment; reduction of the release of toxic substances; the need to introduce the practice of restoring damage to the environment. The implementation of these measures will lead to an increase in the well - being and quality of living of the population. The green economy helps people to use pure environmental services and products.

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